

THEORETICAL EXAMINATION OF CHILL DEPTH CONTROL AND CHILL FORMATION ON THE SURFACE OF DUCTILE IRON

İsmail Ovalı¹, Prof. Dr. Mehmet Erdoğan²

¹Hacettepe University, Hacettepe Vocational School, Technical Drawing Department, Ankara, E-mail: iovali@hacettepe.edu.tr

²Gazi University, Technical Education Faculty, Material and Metallurgy Department, Ankara, E-mail: mehmet@hazi.edu.tr

ABSTRACT

In this study, it is aimed that the examination and production ability of carbidic austempered ductile iron which is a new type of ductile iron by using of mould system with a new designed cooling system. It will be also defined optimum casting condition for optimum wear stress and toughness combination. For this aims, it is focused on a different cooling system from conventional cooling system used in production white cast iron. Therefore, Chill depth and dispersion can be controlled and can be obtained a homogen chill forming. As a theoretical approach, it was understood that chill depth and dispersion on the surface of ductile iron can be controlled and achieved by a mould system with a good designed cooling system. It also seen that the control ability of chill formation enhance mechanical properties of ductile iron especially wear resistance.

Key Words: Ductile iron, Austempered ductile iron, wear resistance, Chill, Cementite.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ductile iron was developed about 40 years ago, but recently it has been replacing millions of tonnes of steel castings and grey iron castings. The major users of ductile iron components include the automotive and machine tool industry. The reason for its popularity is its advantages over steel castings and grey iron castings. For the past few years attempts have been made all over the world to further improve the properties of ductile irons [1].

In the recent years, considerable interest has been shown in the property improvements obtained in ductile iron by austempered heat treatments. Austempered ductile iron (ADI) has a matrix that is a combination of bainitic ferrite and high carbon austenite (transformed stabilized austenite). The combination of strength, ductility, fatigue resistance, machinability and wear resistance makes ADI a unique engineering material that may substitute for steel (cast, forged and/or heat treated) or aluminum in applications where strength/weight ratio is important. Major applications include gears, crankshafts, sprockets, pinions, and other parts used in automotive, earth moving, excavating and agricultural equipment [2-5].

A new type of ADI was improved for especially automotive parts subjected to wear. This new type consist of carbides immersed in the typical ausferritic matrix and called carbidic ADI or CADI. It is expected to enhance wear resistance because of this carbides in matrix. There are some study about CADI and this studies approved that result[6-8]. Chilled cast have also high strength, high hardness, high toughness and high corrosion and wear resistance [9-10].

It is important to control chill depth and dispersion in chilled ductile iron production for optimum mechanical properties. Chill depth and dispersion control has not achieved in previous studies. This knowledge lack in the literature encourage the authors for doing this study.

The aim of this paper is to examine the production ability of chilled ductile iron and define the parameters effecting chill formation of ductile iron. It is also aimed to improve new casting mold for chilled ductile iron and define optimum casting conditions.

2. MATERIAL AND METHOD

2.1 Common Mould System for Chilled Ductile Iron Production

The presences of carbides promote an increase in the abrasion wear resistance, but on the other hand toughness decrease. Therefore, it is important to adjust optimum balance between abrasion resistance and toughness. This goal can be achieved with a mold system which permits control all casting parameters.

The more common methodologies used to obtain chilled ductile iron are shown in figure 1. In this methodology the high undercooling promoted by the use of a chill in the mould. This mould system was used in the most of the literature studies[11-13]. The quantity of graphitizing elements (in particular Si), in order to promote the precipitation of ledeburitic carbides during solidification due to a closer interval between the stable and metastable diagrams can be used in order to obtain microstructure with as-cast carbides [14]. In addition, carbide stabilizing elements, such as chromium, molybdenum or titanium can also be used.[15],

Figure. 1. Common schematic mold model with copper chill at one end which are used for production chilled ductile iron

2.1 New Concept Mould Systems for Chilled Ductile Iron Production

Different mould systems can be improved and designed in order to obtain homogen chill depth and dispersion. Metal mould system can be used and its wall thickness can be changed to control chill formation parameters.

2.1.1 Metal mould system with different wall thickness.

Chilled ductile iron can be produced in a metal mould system which has different wall thickness in order to specify the effect of wall thickness of mould on chill formation tendency (Figure 2).The correlation between wall

thickness and chill depth and dispersion. For example, 5,10 and 20 mm thickness can be selected for this experiment. Therefore, it can be defined how much chill depth can be obtain which wall thickness. In order to improve control ability of chill formation, different material types may be used.

Figure 2. Metal moulds having different wall thickness.

2.1.2 Mould system with cooling system.

A mould system having cooling circulation system on its external surface can be a different solution to figure out chill depth and dispersion control. Chill depth can be controlled with flow rate of liquid. Section of circulation system have also important effect on homogen cooling.

Figure 3. Metal moulds having cooling circulation system.

In order to improve performance of liquid cooling effect on chill formation, it should be used that mould system have different cooling circulations systems. For example, a nozzle system can be assembled on mould surface so that Chill depth control can be adjusted with flow rate and pressure of cooling liquid.

Figure 4. Metal moulds having different nozzle cooling system.

If the desired microstructure cannot be produced this mould system, liquid in the cooling system can be changed. For instance, liquid nitrogen may be used to obtain extreme cooling rate.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chill formation parameters must be well designed and precisely defined in order to obtain desired microstructure and mechanical properties. It can be clearly seen from figure 5 that there are many parameters affect chill formation directly or indirectly. Mould material can be easily used for this aim. It is also the most cheap method for chill control. Cooling rate can be controlled by mould material and mould wall thickness.

Figure 5. Effect of chill tendency parameters on chill formation of ductile iron [14]

A typical microstructure of ductile iron is shown in figure 6. It can be clearly seen that chill formed in ausferritic microstructure. Ausferrite structure can be obtained with austempering heat treatment for optimum combination mechanical properties. In spite of chill formation, chill depth and dispersion control could not be achieved.

Figure 6. A typical microstructure of chilled austempered ductile iron [14]

Center microstructure of part can be adjusted with regard to desired microstructure after obtain controllable chill depth and dispersion (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Schematic microstructure of chilled ductile iron

Result can be summarized with defining important aspect of chill formation parameters on the chill formation tendency;

- Chill depth control and chill dispersion can be achieved by using of new concept mould system.
- Mould material and mould wall thickness are the most feasible parameters for controlling chill depth control and chill dispersion.
- Different mould material can be used to get different chill depth.
- In order to enhance controllability of chill depth and chill dispersion, different cooling system and cooler should be used.
- Optimum wear resistance and strength can be obtain with chilled austempered ductile iron.

4. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors wish to acknowledge the casting applications supports of Estaş Casting Company.

5. REFERENCES

- [1]. Joel, H., “The solidification and corrosion behavior of austempered chilled ductile iron”, Journal of Materials Processing Technology, 101, 159-166, 2000
- [2]. Karsay, S.I., “Ductile iron production and practices”, A.F.S., 45, 133-14, 1979
- [3]. Voigt, R.C., “Ductile iron”, AFS Transactions, 94, 645-986, 1982
- [4]. Moore D.J., Rouns T.N., Rundman K.B., “The relationship between micro structure and tensile properties in austempered ductile irons”, A.F.S. Transactions, 95, 765-774, 1994
- [5]. Voigt R.C., Eldoky, L.M., Chiou, “Ductile iron characterization” H.S, AFS Transactions, 94, 645-649, 1986
- [6]. He, Z.R, Lin, G.X., Ji, S., “Deformation and fracture behavior of cast iron with optimized microstructure”, Materials Characterization, 38, 251-258, 1997
- [7]. Kovacs, B.V., Keough, J.R., “ADI an engineering materials”, Proceedings of the Conference on Advances in High Integrity Castings, Chicago, Illinois, 91-98, 1988
- [8]. Laino, S. J., Sikora, A., Dommarco, R.C., “Development of wear resistant carbidic austempered ductile iron (CADI)”, Wear, 265, 1-7, 2007
- [9]. Leslie, B.A.R., Krause. F.A., Alberts, I., Susil, K., “Influence of Microstructure on High-Cycle Fatigue Behavior of Austempered Ductile Iron”, Material Characterization, 30, 221-234, 1993
- [10]. Kuang, L.C., Chang, C., “Influence Of Heat Treatment On Fatigue Crack Growth Of Austempered Ductile Iron”, Journal Of Mat. Proc. Tec., 37, 54-62, 2002
- [11]. Ceccarelli, B.A., Dommarco, R.C., Mart'inez, R.A., Mart'inez, G.M.R., “Abrasion and impact properties of partially chilled ductile iron”, Wear, 265, 49-55, 2008
- [12]. Giacchi, J.V., Mart'inez, R.A., Dommarco, R.C., “Abrasion and impact properties of partially chilled gray iron”, wear, 262, 282-291, 2007
- [13]. John R. K., Hayrynen K. L., “Agricultural Applications of Austempered Iron Components”, Applied Process Inc. Technologies Div. - Livonia, Michigan, 2009.
- [14]. Dommarco, R.C., Salvande, J.D., “Contact fatigue resistance of austempered and partially chilled ductile irons”, wear 254, 230-236, 2003
- [15]. Hayrynen, K.L., Brandenberg, K.R., Keough, J.R., “Application of austempered cast irons” A.F.S. Transactions, 92, 1-10, 1984

BIOGRAPHIES

İsmail OVALI

İsmail OVALI was born at 19.04.1981 in Burhaniye/Balıkesir .

He graduated from Gazi university, technical education faculty, (2003), Metallurgy Education.B.Sc. Then he took M.Sc Metallurgy Education, Gazi University, institute of science and technology, (2006).After the M.Sc Education, He started the study PhD metallurgy Education, Gazi University, institute of science and technology (2007-).He works at Hacettepe university, Hacettepe vocational school, as lecturer, currently.

His research interests include material science and material characterization, computer aided design,. He presented some presentation in various conferences, as titled below.

OVALI I., KILICLI V., ERDOĞAN M., *Microstructure and Fatigue Properties of Austempered Ductile Iron with Dual Matrix Structure*, CD Proceedings of 14th International Metallurgy and Materials Congress, October 16-19, 2008, Istanbul, Turkey.

AKKURT A., OVALI I., *The effect of burnishing and conventional finishing process on surface roughness and roundness of the AL 6061 aluminum parts* , Pamukkale University Journal of Engineering Sciences, 2009, Turkey.

OVALI I., KILICLI V., ERDOĞAN M., *Fatigue Properties of Austempered Ductile Iron with Dual Matrix Structure*, in preparation,

Mehmet ERDOĞAN

Mehmet ERDOĞAN was born at 20.04.1960 in Gerede/Bolu .

He graduated from Gazi university, technical education faculty, (1978), Metallurgy Education.B.Sc. Then he took M.Sc Metallurgy Education, Gazi University, institute of science and technology, (1986).After the M.Sc Education, He studied PhD metallurgy Education, The University of Manchester, institute of science and technology (1994) following his graduate studies at Gazi university, technical education faculty.

His research interests include material science and material characterization, heat treatment material, ductile iron. He has published some article and in the various conference proceedings, as titled below.

SCI & SSCI & Arts and Humanities

1-Sahin Y., Kilicli V., Ozer M., Erdogan M., A Comparative Study of Abrasive Wear Behaviour of Ductile Iron with Different Dual Matrix Structures, WEAR, 2010, 268(1-2), 153-165,

2- Kilicli V., Erdogan M., “The Nature of the Tensile Fracture in ADI with Dual-Matrix Microstructure”, JOURNAL OF MATERIALS ENGINEERING AND PERFORMANCE, 2010, 268 (1), pp. 153-165.

3- Erdogan M, Kilicli V and Demir B, “Transformation Characteristics of Ductile Iron Austempered From Intercritically Annealing Temperature Ranges”, JOURNAL OF MATERIALS SCIENCE, 2009, Journal of Materials Science 44 (5), pp. 1394-1403.

4- C. Hakan Gür, Melika Ozer, Mehmet Erdogan, “Investigation of the variations in microstructure and mechanical properties of dual-matrix ductile iron by magnetic barkhausen noise analysis”, RESEARCH IN NONDESTRUCTIVE EVALUATION, Volume19, Issue 1, January 2008, Pages 44-60.

5- Kilicli V., Erdogan M., “The Strain-Hardening Behavior of Partially Austenitized and Austempered Ductile Iron with Dual Matrix Structures”, JOURNAL OF MATERIALS ENGINEERING AND PERFORMANCE, 2008, 17 (2), pp. 240-249.

6- Y. Sahin, M. Erdogan, M. Cerah, Effect of martensite volume fraction and tempering time on abrasive wear of ferritic ductile iron with dual matrix, 2008, WEAR, (1-2), pp. 196-202.

7 - B. Demir, M. Erdogan, The hardenability of austenite with different alloy content and dispersion in dual phase steels, JOURNAL OF MATERIALS PROCESSING TECHNOLOGY, 2008, 208 (1-3), pp. 75-84.

8- Erdogan M., Kilicli V., “Tensile Fracture Behavior Austempered Ductile Iron with Dual Matrix Structures”, JOURNAL OF MATERIALS ENGINEERING AND PERFORMANCE, 2008, 17 (2), pp. 240-249.

- 9- Erdogan M., Kilicli V., Demir B., “The Influence of Austenite Dispersion on Phase Transformation During Austempering in Ductile Cast Iron with Dual Matrix Structure”, RESEARCH IN MATERIALS SCIENCE, 2008, 99 (7), pp. 751-760.
- 10- Kocatepe K, Cerah K and Erdogan M, “The Tensile Fracture Behaviour of Intercritically Annealed and Quenched+Tempered Ferritic Ductile Iron with Dual Matrix Structure, accepted for publication”, MATERIALS & DESIGN 28 (1): 172-181 2007.
- 11- M. Kaplan, C.H. Gür, M. Erdogan, “Characterization of Dual-Phase Steels Using Magnetic Barkhausen Noise Technique”, J NONDESTRUCT EVAL (2007) 26: 79–87.
- 12- Kilicli V., Erdogan M., “The Effect of Ausferrite Volume Fraction and its Morphology on The Tensile Properties of Partially Austenitized and Austempered Ductile Irons with Dual Matrix Structures”, International JOURNAL OF CAST METAL RESEARCH, 2007 VOL 20 NO 4 202-214.
- 13- Y. Sahin, M. Erdogan and V. Kilicli, “Wear behaviour of austempered ductile irons with dual matrix structures”, JOURNAL OF MATERIALS SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING A, 444 (2007) 31–38.
- 14- Erdogan M, Cerah M and Kocatepe K, “Influence of Intercritical Austenitising and Tempering Time and Martensite Volume Fractions on Tensile Properties of Ferritic Ductile Iron with Dual Matrix Structure”, INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CAST METALS RESEARCH 19 (4): 248-253 SEP 2006.
- 15- Kocatepe K, Cerah M and Erdogan M, “Effect of Martensite Volume Fraction And Its Morphology On The Tensile Properties of Ferritic Ductile Iron With Dual Matrix Structures”, JOURNAL OF MATERIALS PROCESSING TECHNOLOGY 178 (1-3): 44- 51 SEP 14 2006.
- 16- Kilicli V and Erdogan M, “Tensile Properties of Partially Austenitized and Austempered Ductile Irons with Dual Matrix Structures”, MATERIALS SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY 22 (8): 919-928 AUG 2006.
- 17- Cerah M, Kocatepe K and Erdogan M, “Influence of Martensite Volume Fraction and Tempering Time on Tensile Properties of Partially Austenitized in The (W+X) Temperature Range and Quenched +Tempered Ferritic Ductile Iron”, JOURNAL OF MATERIALS SCIENCE, 40 (2005) 3453 – 3459.
- 18- Tekel_ S., Erdogan M, Aktas, Bulent, Influence of W-Al₂O₃ addition on sintering and grain growth behaviour of 8 mol% Y₂O₃-stabilised cubic zirconia (c-ZrO₂), CERAMICS INTERNATIONAL 30 (2004) 2203–2209.
- 19- Tekel_ S., Erdogan M, Aktas Microstructural evolution in 8 mol% Y₂O₃-stabilized cubic zirconia (8YSCZ) with SiO₂ addition MATERIALS SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING A 386 (2004) 1-9.
- 20- Erdogan. M, Tekeli, S, The effect of martensite volume fraction and particle size on tensile properties of surface-carburised AISI 8620 Steel with dual phase core microstructure, MATERIALS CHARACTERIZATION , 49(2003) 445-454.
- 21- Erdogan. M, The effect of austenite dispersion on phase transformation in dual phase steels. SCRIPTA MATER 48 (5): 501-506 Mar 3 2003.
- 22- Erdogan. M, Priestner R, Effect of martensite content, its dispersion, and epitaxial ferrite content on Bauschinger behaviour of dual phase steel, MATERIALS SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, April, 2002, Vol.16, pp: 369-376.
- 23- Erdogan. M, Tekeli S, Pamuk O, And Erkan A, Surface carburised AISI 8620 Steel with dual phase core microstructure, MATERIALS SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, August 2002, Vol.18,pp: 840-844.
- 24- Erdogan. M, The effect of new ferrite content on the tensile fracture behaviour of dual phase steels J MATER SCI 37 (17): 3623-3630 SEP . 2002.
- 25- Tekeli, S, Erdogan. M, A quantitative assesment of cavities in 3 mol% yttria-stabilized tetragonal zirconia specimens containing various grain size, CERAMICS INTERNATIONAL, Vol 28 (7), pp: 785-789, 2002.
- 26- Erdogan. M, Tekeli, S, The effect of martensite particle size on tensile fracture of surface-carburised AISI 8620 Steel with dual phase core microstructure, MATERIALS & DESIGN, Vol 23, pp: 597-604, 2002.
- 27- Erdogan. M, Priestner. R, Effect of epitaxial ferrite yielding and plastic flow in dual phase steel in tension and compression, MATERIALS SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, November, 1999, Vol.15, pp: 1273-1284.
- International Symposium
- 1- Sahin Y., Kilicli V., Ozer M., Erdogan M., A Comparative Study of Abrasive Wear Behaviour of Ductile Iron with Different Dual Matrix Structures, WEAR, 2010, 268(1-2), 153-165,
- 2- Kilicli V., Erdogan M., “The Nature of the Tensile Fracture in ADI with Dual-Matrix Microstructure”, JOURNAL OF MATERIALS ENGINEERING AND PERFORMANCE, 2010, 268 (1), pp. 153-165.
- 3- Erdogan M, Kilicli V and Demir B, “Transformation Characteristics of Ductile Iron Austempered From Intercritically Annealing Temperature Ranges”, JOURNAL OF MATERIALS SCIENCE, 2009, Journal of Materials Science 44 (5), pp. 1394-1403.

- 4- C. Hakan Gür, Melika Ozer, Mehmet Erdogan, “Investigation of the variations in microstructure and mechanical properties of dual-matrix ductile iron by magnetic barkhausen noise analysis”, RESEARCH IN NONDESTRUCTIVE EVALUATION, Volume 19, Issue 1, January 2008, Pages 44-60.
- 5- Kilicli V., Erdogan M., “The Strain-Hardening Behavior of Partially Austenitized and Austempered Ductile Iron with Dual Matrix Structures”, JOURNAL OF MATERIALS ENGINEERING AND PERFORMANCE, 2008, 17 (2), pp. 240-249.
- 6- Y. Sahin, M. Erdogan, M. Cerah, Effect of martensite volume fraction and tempering time on abrasive wear of ferritic ductile iron with dual matrix, 2008, WEAR, (1-2), pp. 196-202.
- 7 - B. Demir, M. Erdogan, The hardenability of austenite with different alloy content and dispersion in dual phase steels, JOURNAL OF MATERIALS PROCESSING TECHNOLOGY, 2008, 208 (1-3), pp. 75-84.
- 8- Erdogan M., Kilicli V., “Tensile Fracture Behavior Austempered Ductile Iron with Dual Matrix Structures”, JOURNAL OF MATERIALS ENGINEERING AND PERFORMANCE, 2008, 17 (2), pp. 240-249.
- 9- Erdogan M., Kilicli V., Demir B., “The Influence of Austenite Dispersion on Phase Transformation During Austempering in Ductile Cast Iron with Dual Matrix Structure”, RESEARCH IN MATERIALS SCIENCE, 2008, 99 (7), pp. 751-760.
- 10- Kocatepe K, Cerah K and Erdogan M, “The Tensile Fracture Behaviour of Intercritically Annealed and Quenched+Tempered Ferritic Ductile Iron with Dual Matrix Structure, accepted for publication”, MATERIALS & DESIGN 28 (1): 172-181 2007.
- 11- M. Kaplan, C.H. Gür, M. Erdogan, “Characterization of Dual-Phase Steels Using Magnetic Barkhausen Noise Technique”, J NONDESTRUCT EVAL (2007) 26: 79–87.
- 12- Kilicli V., Erdogan M., “The Effect of Ausferrite Volume Fraction and its Morphology on The Tensile Properties of Partially Austenitized and Austempered Ductile Irons with Dual Matrix Structures”, International JOURNAL OF CAST METAL RESEARCH, 2007 VOL 20 NO 4 202-214.
- 13- Y. Sahin, M. Erdogan and V. Kilicli, “Wear behaviour of austempered ductile irons with dual matrix structures”, JOURNAL OF MATERIALS SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING A, 444 (2007) 31–38.
- 14- Erdogan M, Cerah M and Kocatepe K, “Influence of Intercritical Austenitising and Tempering Time and Martensite Volume Fractions on Tensile Properties of Ferritic Ductile Iron with Dual Matrix Structure”, INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CAST METALS RESEARCH 19 (4): 248-253 SEP 2006.
- 15- Kocatepe K, Cerah M and Erdogan M, “Effect of Martensite Volume Fraction And Its Morphology On The Tensile Properties of Ferritic Ductile Iron With Dual Matrix Structures”, JOURNAL OF MATERIALS PROCESSING TECHNOLOGY 178 (1-3): 44- 51 SEP 14 2006.
- 16- Kilicli V and Erdogan M, “Tensile Properties of Partially Austenitized and Austempered Ductile Irons with Dual Matrix Structures”, MATERIALS SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY 22 (8): 919-928 AUG 2006.
- 17- Cerah M, Kocatepe K and Erdogan M, “Influence of Martensite Volume Fraction and Tempering Time on Tensile Properties of Partially Austenitized in The (W+X) Temperature Range and Quenched +Tempered Ferritic Ductile Iron”, JOURNAL OF MATERIALS SCIENCE, 40 (2005) 3453 – 3459.
- 18- Tekel_ S., Erdogan M, Aktas, Bulent, Influence of W-Al2O3 addition on sintering and grain growth behaviour of 8 mol% Y2O3-stabilised cubic zirconia (c-ZrO2), CERAMICS INTERNATIONAL 30 (2004) 2203–2209.
- 19- Tekel_ S., Erdogan M, Aktas Microstructural evolution in 8 mol% Y2O3-stabilized cubic zirconia (8YSCZ) with SiO2 addition MATERIALS SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING A 386 (2004) 1-9.
- 20- Erdogan. M, Tekeli, S, The effect of martensite volume fraction and particle size on tensile properties of surface-carburised AISI 8620 Steel with dual phase core microstructure, MATERIALS CHARACTERIZATION , 49(2003) 445-454.
- 21- Erdogan. M, The effect of austenite dispersion on phase transformation in dual phase steels. SCRIPTA MATER 48 (5): 501-506 Mar 3 2003.
- 22- Erdogan. M, Priestner R, Effect of martensite content, its dispersion, and epitaxial ferrite content on Bauschinger behaviour of dual phase steel, MATERIALS SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, April, 2002, Vol.16, pp: 369-376.
- 23- Erdogan. M, Tekeli S, Pamuk O, And Erkan A, Surface carburised AISI 8620 Steel with dual phase core microstructure, MATERIALS SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, August 2002, Vol.18,pp: 840-844.
- 24- Erdogan. M, The effect of new ferrite content on the tensile fracture behaviour of dual phase steels J MATER SCI 37 (17): 3623-3630 SEP . 2002.

13th International Materials Symposium (IMSP'2010)
13-15th October 2010 – Pamukkale University – Denizli - Turkey

- 25- Tekeli, S, Erdogan. M, A quantitative assesment of cavities in 3 mol% yttria-stabilized tetragonal zirconia specimens containing various grain size, CERAMICS INTERNATIONAL, Vol 28 (7), pp: 785-789, 2002.
- 26- Erdogan. M, Tekeli, S, The effect of martensite particle size on tensile fracture of surface-carburised AISI 8620 Steel with dual phase core microstructure, MATERIALS & DESIGN, Vol 23, pp: 597-604, 2002.
- 27- Erdogan. M, Priestner. R, Effect of epitaxial ferrite yielding and plastic flow in dual phase steel in tension and compression, MATERIALS SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY, November, 1999, Vol.15, pp: 1273-1284